

Concurrent Estimation of Ship Transfer Functions and Incoming Waves by Using Response Measurements

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Abstract. Estimating the incoming waves onboard is of importance to ensure effective ship operation and safety. This paper is concerned with a response-based wave estimation method, in which incoming waves are inversely estimated based on measured responses via their transfer functions (TRFs), commonly referred to as the 'Wave Buoy Analogy (WBA)'. Specifically, a phase-resolved WBA technique presented by the authors' preceding study is referenced. The accuracy of estimated waves via the WBA is in essence contingent upon the accuracy of TRFs of the responses used. However, it is difficult to accurately estimate the TRFs onboard, as the weight distribution and operational condition would change from voyage to voyage. To address this issue, this paper proposes a novel approach to simultaneously attain estimations of ship response TRFs and incoming wave profiles, making use of measured ship responses. Specifically, parametrized TRFs are devised, and then the parameters which characterize the TRFs are identified through optimization with reference to reconstructed phase-resolved incident waves. A closed-form expression (CFE) and linear strip theory, the so-called New Strip Method (NSM) are used to parametrize the TRF, named as parametrized transfer function (P-TRF). The validity of the present approach is validated against experimental campaigns using scaled models of a bulk carrier and container ship. It turned out that the estimation results of TRFs using the NSM-based P-TRF demonstrates a high degree of correlation with the experimental measurements, whereas the CFE-based P-TRF exhibits a notable inability to estimate the phase components of the TRFs. Estimations based on the NSM-based P-TRF are also proved to be effective to estimate incident wave profiles, particularly low frequency wave components.

Keywords: *Ship Response, Transfer Function, Wave Reconstruction, Closed-form Expression, Strip Theory*

1. Introduction

Estimating ocean waves plays an important role in the safety of ships and offshore structures, as well as their efficient operation and maneuvering. Operators can access the ocean wave hindcast database, such as ERA5 database [1], to know the wave spectra together with directionality of waves. Hindcast databases are, however, somewhat sparse to accurately capture the waves encountered during voyage for ships and, moreover, are not suitable for real-time predictions. Besides, the time-domain information pertaining to the waves, specifically the incoming wave profiles, is unavailable from the hindcast data.

The so-called wave-buoy analogy (WBA) technique [2-5] is known for its effectiveness to capture waves onboard, both in encountered and absolute frequency domains. One basic and common strategy of the WBA techniques is that the waves are inversely estimated by using measured ship responses, via pre-estimated transfer functions. The WBA has been extensively employed in a variety of applications, including the prediction of other (unmeasured) ship responses [6, 7], and the complement of other wave buoy measurements [8]. Our research group addressed an extension of WBA towards phase-resolved wave estimation, with the aim of reconstructing wave profiles [9, 10].

Irrespective of the WBA technique employed, it is a common issue that the accuracy of estimated waves by the WBA is dependent on the precision of transfer functions (TRFs) of ship responses used for estimation. Use of well-validated seakeeping codes, such as the strip theory [11] or the three-dimensional boundary element method (BEM) [12], with a hull profile and weight distribution as the input, may offer TRFs at a practically acceptable level. However, it is not always feasible to obtain an accurate hull profile for all vessels, and weight distributions

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often vary from one voyage to the next, which makes it challenging to obtain precise inputs for the seakeeping computation. To resolve this issue, Nielsen et al. [13] proposed an online tuning method of TRFs using a parametrized TRF (P-TRF) based on a closed-form expression (CFE) proposed by Jensen et al. [14]. In the method, the parameters that characterize the CFE-based P-TRFs are identified by utilizing the ERA5 measurements. Following this, Mounet et al. [15] devised a simultaneous approach for TRF tuning and sea state estimation by exploiting a conventional WBA technique in frequency domain. However, the methodologies outlined in refs. [13, 15] are exclusively focused on the calibration of amplitudes of the P-TRF, and do not encompass the phase components of the P-TRF; noticing that *both* amplitudes and phase components of the TRFs are needed in the WBA for optimal estimation of the wave conditions.

This background motivated us to establish an online estimation method of TRFs including the phase components, see Takami et al. [16]. In the proposed methodology, multiple response measurements are referenced to identify the parameters in the P-TRF through the phase-resolved wave reconstruction method [9]. Upon identification of the parameters, the incoming wave profiles can be concurrently reconstructed. Although ref. [16] employed the CFE to characterize the P-TRF, any seakeeping code may be incorporated if the TRF can be characterized by parameters. In ref. [16], a numerical demonstration was presented in situations where true TRF is fully represented by a CFE. Our next challenge is to experimentally demonstrate the validity of the methodology in ref. [16], by using tank test measurements. However, the phase of the TRF obtained by CFE may be overly simplified to capture realistic phenomena, as only a simplified phase shift was incorporated into the CFE-based P-TRF at the stage presented in ref. [16].

This paper presents experimental validation of the methodology for concurrent estimation of TRFs and incoming waves devised in ref. [16]. In formulating the P-TRF, this paper also introduces linear strip theory, the so-called ‘New Strip Theory (NSM)’ [11]. Utilization of NSM obviates the necessity for the hull profile to be used as an input, with only the cross-sectional area at each strip being sufficient for use as an input through the Lewis Form approximation. Experimental campaigns using scaled models of a bulk carrier and container ship are referenced. Estimation results based on the CFE- and NSM-based P-TRF are compared with the experimental measurements as reference.

2. Parametrized Transfer Function (P-TRF)

2.1. CFE-based characterization

According to Jensen et al. [14] and Mansour et al. [17], the amplitude components of TRFs of heave (Φ_h) and pitch (Φ_θ) motions are given as:

$$\begin{aligned}\Phi_h &= \eta |F| \\ \Phi_\theta &= \eta |G|\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

with

$$\begin{aligned}\eta &= \left\{ \sqrt{(1 - 2kT\alpha^2)^2 + \left(\frac{A^2}{kB\alpha^2}\right)^2} \right\}^{-1} \\ F &= \kappa f \frac{2}{k_e L} \sin\left(\frac{k_e L}{2}\right) \\ G &= \kappa f \frac{24}{(k_e L)^2} \left[\sin\left(\frac{k_e L}{2}\right) - \frac{k_e L}{2} \cos\left(\frac{k_e L}{2}\right) \right] \\ k_e &= |k \cos \beta| \\ f &= \sqrt{(1 - kT)^2 + \left(\frac{A^2}{kB\alpha^3}\right)^2}\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

where k denotes the wave number, L the ship length, B the breadth, T the draught, and β the heading angle. κ is the Smith correction factor approximated by

$$\kappa = \exp(-kT),\tag{3}$$

A is the dimensionless ratio between the incoming and diffracted waves given by

$$A = 2 \sin\left(\frac{1}{2} k B \alpha^2\right) \exp(-k T \alpha^2), \quad (4)$$

and α is a parameter related to the encounter frequency ω_e , ship speed V , wave frequency ω , wave number k , and the heading angle β by:

$$\omega_e = \omega - k V \cos \beta = |\alpha| \omega \quad (5)$$

If the block coefficient C_b is less than one, the breadth B is replaced by $B C_b$.

The TRF for VBM amidships was also proposed in Jensen et al. [14]. The amplitude component Φ_v is given by:

$$\Phi_v = \kappa \frac{1-kT}{(k_e L)^2} \left[1 - \cos\left(\frac{k_e L}{2}\right) - \frac{k_e L}{4} \sin\left(\frac{k_e L}{2}\right) \right] F_v(F_n) F_C(C_b)^3 \sqrt{|\cos \beta|} \quad (6)$$

where the correction factors F_v and F_C are given by:

$$F_v(F_n) = 1 + 3F_n^2 \quad (7)$$

$$F_C(C_b) = (1 - \vartheta)^2 + 0.6\vartheta(2 - \vartheta) \quad (8)$$

where $\vartheta = 2.5\{1 - \max(0.6, C_b)\}$

where F_n denotes the Froude number.

Phase components of the heave and pitch motions were provided by Mansour et al. [17]. The phase angle of the forcing function is:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos(\varepsilon_f) &= \frac{1-kT}{f} \\ \sin(\varepsilon_f) &= \frac{A^2}{k B \alpha^3 f} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The phase angle for the heave and the pitch motions relative to the forcing function is:

$$\begin{aligned} \cos(\varepsilon_w) &= (1 - 2kT \alpha^2) \eta \\ \sin(\varepsilon_w) &= -\frac{A^2}{k B \alpha^2} \eta \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Then, the phase components of heave (Γ_h) and pitch (Γ_θ) motions are:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_h &= \varepsilon_f + \varepsilon_w \\ \Gamma_\theta &= \varepsilon_f + \varepsilon_w + \frac{\pi}{2} + \varepsilon_p \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where ε_p denotes the phase shift for pitch motion. The phase component of VBM is simplified as having a phase difference of ε_v with Γ_h . Thus,

$$\Gamma_v = \varepsilon_f + \varepsilon_w + \varepsilon_v \quad (12)$$

Parameters $\{L, B, T, V, \beta, C_b, \varepsilon_p, \varepsilon_v\}$ are used to characterize the P-TRF.

2.2. NSM-based characterization

Apart from the CFE-based characterization of P-TRF, the NSM is introduced to compute the P-TRF. The NSM used in the present study is based on the following assumptions:

- Slender body approximation for ship hull form.
- Radiation flow is used to compute diffraction forces.
- Inviscid, incompressible and irrotational fluid.

Furthermore, in this specific study, cross sections of a vessel are approximated by using Lewis form. The parameters L, B, T, V are introduced as like the CFE-based case. In order to express the distribution of the cross-sectional areas along the longitudinal direction, the following weighting function, designated as μ , is introduced.

$$\mu(x/L) = \exp\left\{-\frac{2(x/L)^2}{10^{2\gamma-2}}\right\} \quad (13)$$

where x denotes the longitudinal position of the cross-section where $x = 0$ indicates the midship, γ the parameter to adjust the distribution of μ in the longitudinal direction. The cross-sectional area A_c at the nondimensional x/L is then defined by:

$$A_c(x/L) = \mu(x/L)BT \quad (14)$$

Note that the draft and breadth remain constant along the longitudinal direction to reduce the number of parameters and to avoid generating unrealistic hull forms due to certain parameter combinations. The weighting function μ for $\gamma = 0.75, 0.9$, and 1.1 are depicted in Figure 1. Using A_c placed in the longitudinal direction, the block coefficient C_b is calculated by computing the displacement of the ship. 21 cross sections are used for NSM computation. Introducing $\gamma = 0.75, 0.9$, and 1.1 , the respective C_b values are $C_b = 0.65, 0.79$, and 0.9 . The factor γ is further introduced to characterize the P-TRF, i.e., the parameters in the NSM-based P-TRF are $\{L, B, T, V, \beta, \gamma\}$.

Figure 1. Weighting function μ (Eq. (13)) to define the cross-sectional area at each section.

3. Parameter identification

Distinct $k = \{1, 2, \dots, K\}$ measured wave-induced responses R_k^m can be fitted by the linear superposition of trigonometric functions as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} R_k^m(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^M \sigma_{k,i}^m \{u_{i,k}^m \cos(\omega_{i,e} t) - \bar{u}_{i,k}^m \sin(\omega_{i,e} t)\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^M \sqrt{PSD_k(\omega_i)} d\omega_i \{u_{i,k}^m \cos(\omega_i t) - \bar{u}_{i,k}^m \sin(\omega_i t)\} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where PSD_k denotes the powerspectrum density of the k -th response. $M = 1001$ wave components are introduced with an equidistant frequency increment of $d\omega_i = d\omega = 0.002$ rad/s. $\{u_{i,k}^m, \bar{u}_{i,k}^m\}$ are the phase components of the k -th response, which can be detected by using Prolate Spheroidal Wave Functions (PSWF) [9]. Given K responses, the incident wave profile amidships within a given short-time window of $-T_e \leq t \leq T_e$ is [9]:

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta^e(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^M \sqrt{S^e(\omega_i)} d\omega_i \{v_i^e \cos(\omega_i t) - \bar{v}_i^e \sin(\omega_i t)\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\sqrt{PSD_k(\omega_i)} d\omega_i \Phi_k(\omega_i, \beta)}{\Phi_{k,max}} \{u_{i,k}^e \cos(\omega_i t - \Gamma_k(\omega_i, \beta)) - \bar{u}_{i,k}^e \sin(\omega_i t - \Gamma_k(\omega_i, \beta))\}}{\sum_{k=1}^K \left\{ \frac{\Phi_k(\omega_i, \beta)}{\Phi_{k,max}} \right\}^2}\end{aligned}\quad (16)$$

For all the cases in this study, $T_e = 300$ s is used with a sampling frequency of 3.3Hz. $\Phi_{k,max}$ is the maximum amplitude of TRF:

$$\Phi_{k,max} = \max\{\Phi_k(\omega_i, \beta)\} \quad (17)$$

The reconstructed waves by Eq. (16) may be noisy if the denominator in Eq. (16) is extremely small. Thus, the following criterion α_f to the denominator in Eq. (16) is introduced to avoid numerical errors:

$$\sum_{k=1}^K \left\{ \frac{\Phi_k(\omega_i, \beta)}{\Phi_{k,max}} \right\}^2 > \alpha_f^2 \quad (18)$$

Only frequency components fulfilling Eq. (18) are kept in the reconstructed wave by Eq. (16). In compliance with ref. [9], $\alpha_f = 0.1$ is adopted. The power spectrum density S^e and phase components $\{v_i^e, \bar{v}_i^e\}$ of ζ^e are then given by:

$$\begin{aligned}S^e(\omega_i) &= \frac{\pi}{2T_e d\omega^2} \{H_1^2 + H_2^2\} \\ v_i^e &= \frac{H_1}{\sqrt{S^e(\omega_i) d\omega}}, \quad \bar{v}_i^e = \frac{H_2}{\sqrt{S^e(\omega_i) d\omega}} \\ \text{where } H_1 &= \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\sqrt{PSD_k(\omega_i)} d\omega_i \Phi_k(\omega_i, \beta)}{\Phi_{k,max}} \{u_{i,k}^e \cos(\Gamma_k(\omega_i, \beta)) + \bar{u}_{i,k}^e \sin(\Gamma_k(\omega_i, \beta))\}}{\sum_{k=1}^K \left\{ \frac{\Phi_k(\omega_i, \beta)}{\Phi_{k,max}} \right\}^2} \\ H_2 &= \frac{\sum_{k=1}^K \frac{\sqrt{PSD_k(\omega_i)} d\omega_i \Phi_k(\omega_i, \beta)}{\Phi_{k,max}} \{u_{i,k}^e \cos(\Gamma_k(\omega_i, \beta)) - \bar{u}_{i,k}^e \sin(\Gamma_k(\omega_i, \beta))\}}{\sum_{k=1}^K \left\{ \frac{\Phi_k(\omega_i, \beta)}{\Phi_{k,max}} \right\}^2}\end{aligned}\quad (19)$$

Thus, the ship responses induced by the reconstructed waves by Eq. (16) can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}R_k^e(t) &= \sum_{i=1}^M \sigma_{k,i}^e \left\{ v_i^e \cos(\omega_{i,e} t + \Gamma_k(\omega_{i,e}, \beta)) - \bar{v}_i^e \sin(\omega_{i,e} t + \Gamma_k(\omega_{i,e}, \beta)) \right\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^M \Phi_k(\omega_i, \beta) \sqrt{S^e(\omega_i)} d\omega_i \left\{ v_i^e \cos(\omega_i t + \Gamma_k(\omega_i, \beta)) - \bar{v}_i^e \sin(\omega_i t + \Gamma_k(\omega_i, \beta)) \right\}\end{aligned}\quad (20)$$

The measured responses through the fitting by Eq. (15) and reconstructed ones by Eq. (20) coincide within the frequency ranges of interest restricted by Eq. (18), provided that exact TRFs Φ_k and Γ_k have been incorporated. Therefore, the parameters that characterize the P-TRFs are to be identified so that they minimize errors between Eqs. (15) and (20). In the present study, the parameters in the P-TRF are identified by nonlinear optimization. Referring to discretized values of R_k^m and R_k^e , a cost function is defined as:

$$J = \sum_{k=1}^K \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^N (R_{k,j}^m - R_{k,j}^e)^2}{N}} + \sum_{k=1}^K \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^M (\sigma_{k,i}^m - \sigma_{k,i}^e)^2}{M}} \quad (21)$$

where N denotes the number of samples. This study introduces three distinct responses, i.e., heave, pitch, and VBM, resulting in a total of $K = 3$ responses. As a side note, a small sensitivity study was conducted using only heave and pitch (i.e., $K = 2$); however, the optimization did not function properly in identifying a valid solution. The introduction of VBM strengthened the computational stability. In this study, the cost function is calculated within $-0.5T_e \leq t < 0.5T_e$ to get rid of wave reconstruction errors [9], thereby $N = 1001$. The cost function J is a function of $\{L, B, T, V, \beta, C_b, \varepsilon_p, \varepsilon_v\}$ when CFE-based P-TRF is used, while is a function of $\{L, B, T, V, \beta, \gamma\}$ when NSM-based P-TRF is used. $\bar{R}_{k,j}^m$ and $\bar{R}_{k,j}^e$ denote the discretized and normalized R_k^m and R_k^e according to:

$$\bar{R}_k^m = \frac{R_k^m - \mu_k^m}{\max\{R_k^m\} - \min\{R_k^m\}}, \bar{R}_k^e = \frac{R_k^e - \mu_k^m}{\max\{R_k^m\} - \min\{R_k^m\}} \quad (22)$$

where μ_k^m denotes the mean value of R_k^m during $-0.5T_e \leq t < 0.5T_e$. As indicated in Eq. (22), normalization of R_k^e is also made by referring to μ_k^m , $\max\{R_k^m\}$, and $\min\{R_k^m\}$. In the same manner, $\bar{\sigma}_{k,i}^m$ and $\bar{\sigma}_{k,i}^e$ are:

$$\bar{\sigma}_{k,i}^m = \frac{\sigma_{k,i}^m}{\max\{\sigma_k^m\}}, \bar{\sigma}_{k,i}^e = \frac{\sigma_{k,i}^e}{\max\{\sigma_k^m\}} \quad (23)$$

using the maximum values of $\sigma_{k,i}^m$ for $i = 1, \dots, M$.

Estimations of TRFs are made by identifying the parameters in which $\min\{J\}$ is attained. In our preceding study in ref. [15], a global optimization algorithm based on Genetic Algorithm (GA) provided accurate solutions, but GA may be unreal for practical application as the computational burden is too large. A local optimization algorithm based on the Nelder-Mead (NM) algorithm was found to be effective and efficient if plausible initial values can be obtained. Thus, in the present study, the NM algorithm implemented by the Matlab function *fminsearch* is applied for optimization, where the initial values are selected from the principal particulars of the vessel. The maximum number of iterations is set at 200, and the optimization process is terminated when the extent of changes in the cost function J and each parameter is less than $1e-4$.

As the P-TRF offers the TRFs with the absolute frequency $\omega_{i,0}$ as the input, a frequency mapping from the encountered frequency $\omega_{i,e}$ is required, if the vessel has a forward speed. However, the following/oblique following seas, i.e. $\beta < 90$ deg or $\beta > 270$ deg cases, are beset by a well-known three-to-one mapping problem (Nielsen et al. [13]). Thus, in this study, the Doppler shift is only accounted for in head/oblique head sea cases, i.e., $90 \leq \beta \leq 270$ deg. Otherwise, the P-TRF is computed by “forcing” $V = 0$ m/s and $\omega_{i,0} = \omega_{i,e}$. Hence, in computing the TRFs $\{\Phi_k, \Gamma_k\}$ by using the P-TRF, the following frequency conversion is applied if $90 \leq \beta \leq 270$ deg,

$$\omega_{i,0} = \frac{1}{2\psi} \left(1 - \sqrt{1 - 4\Psi\omega_{i,e}}\right), \text{ where } \Psi = \frac{v \cos \beta}{g} \quad (24)$$

where g denotes the acceleration of gravity. Considering the Doppler shift, $\Phi_k(\omega_{i,e}, \beta) = \langle \Phi_k(\omega_{i,0}, \beta) \rangle_{\omega_{i,e}}$ and $\Gamma_k(\omega_{i,e}, \beta) = \langle \Gamma_k(\omega_{i,0}, \beta) \rangle_{\omega_{i,e}}$ are used for computing Eq. (16). The overall procedure of the present approach is summarized in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Schematic of the present approach for concurrent estimation of incident wave and TRFs.

4. Experimental Campaigns

4.1. Bulk carrier model *with* (non-zero) forward speed

An experimental campaign conducted as a part of the R&D project in Japan (Fujikubo et al. [18]) is referenced to demonstrate the validity of the present approach. Towing tank tests using a scaled bulk carrier model were carried out in the Actual Sea Model Basin (ASMB), National Maritime Research Institute. A picture of the model and its principal particulars are shown in Figure 3 (scale ratio: 1/72). Henceforth, all relevant physical values will be denoted in full scale.

Response measurements of heave, pitch, and VBM amidships in oblique following seas ($\beta = 240$ deg) with forward speed $V = 2.57$ m/s (= 5 kt) in long-crested irregular waves were collected during the test. The incident wave spectrum is $H_s = 8$ m and $T_z = 12$ s, the Pierson-Moskowitz type. Data with a duration of 600 s were collected at a sampling frequency of 24 Hz and are re-sampled to 3.3 Hz. TRFs of the model were measured by carrying out the tests in regular waves of different frequencies, and then the measured amplitude and phase components of the TRFs are used for validation of the TRF estimation by the present approach.

Principal particulars	Values in full scale
Ship length	278 m
Breadth	45 m
Draught	17.7 m
Block coefficient	0.844

Figure 3. Scaled model of the bulk carrier and principal particulars in full scale.

4.2. Container ship model without forward speed

Experimental measurements of a scaled model of a Post-Panamax size container ship (6600 TEU) are also referenced; serving to demonstrate the applicability of the approach to a modern slender ship. The tank test was again carried out in the ASMB, National Maritime Research Institute. Figure 4 depicts the model overview and its principal particulars; the model is the same as used in Takami et al. [19]. Referring to the scale ratio of the model (1/100), all relevant physical values will henceforth be denoted in full scale, unless otherwise stated.

The model is installed at the center of the basin and is connected to a towing carriage and a rotary table via two rods, as illustrated in Figure 5, noticing that this study makes use of experimental measurements conducted at zero forward speed exclusively. Three degree-of-freedom (DOF) ship motions, i.e. heave, pitch, and roll motions, were allowed and measured, while the other motions were constrained. The VBM was measured via a beam specimen installed amidship, see ref. [19]. Hydroelastic vibrations in the measured VBM were filtered out by applying a low-pass filter with a threshold frequency of 2.0 rad/s in full scale. The relative wave direction was altered by means of a rotary table rotation, while keeping the absolute orientation of the incident waves. Response measurements in long-crested irregular waves at $\beta = 0, 180, 210, 240, 300,$ and 330 deg were made with a zero forward speed. The incident wave spectrum is $H_s = 5$ m and $T_z = 7.5$ s, the Pierson-Moskowitz type. Data were collected at a sampling frequency of 10 Hz and are re-sampled with 3.3 Hz. Measurements were taken for 1800 s in each relative wave direction. Incident wave profiles were measured by two wave gauges mounted at 2.0 m (in model scale) away from amidship, see Figure 5, and the averaged values from two gauges are referenced for validation of wave profile reconstruction by the present approach.

Principal particulars	Values in full scale
Ship length	283.8 m
Breadth	42.8 m
Draught	14.0 m
Block coefficient	0.64

Figure 4. Scaled model of a container ship and its principal particulars in full scale.

Figure 5. Installation of ship model and wave gauges in the model basin.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1. Bulk carrier model test ($V = 5$ m/s)

Introducing the heave, pitch, and VBM measurements as R_1^m , R_2^m , and R_3^m into Eq. (15), respectively, the TRFs are identified via the present procedure. In reference to the principal particulars in Figure 3 and the phase shifts presented by Mansour et al. [17], $\{L, B, T, V, \beta, C_b, \varepsilon_p, \varepsilon_v\} = \{278, 45, 17.7, 5.0, 240, 0.844, 0, -\pi\}$ and $\{L, B, T, V, \beta, \gamma\} = \{278, 45, 17.7, 5.0, 240, 1.0\}$ are used as the initial guesses for optimization using CFE- and NSM-based P-TRFs, respectively.

Figures 6 and 7 show the estimation results of TRFs through the utilization of the CFE- and NSM-based P-TRFs, in comparison with experimental measurements. For comparison, the NSM-based P-TRF estimations by introducing the parameters $\{L, B, T, V, \beta, \gamma\} = \{278, 45, 17.7, 5.0, 240, 1.0\}$ are included (which are also used as the initial guess for optimization), referred to as ‘Original’ in the figures. From the results, the CFE-based estimation results are evidently inferior to the NSM-based estimation results, particularly in regard to the phase components, see Figure 7. The present CFE-based P-TRF introduces the frequency-independent phase shifts (i.e. $\varepsilon_p, \varepsilon_v$), which precludes a flexible representation of the phase components. Incorporating frequency-dependent phase shifts as parameters of the P-TRF would serve to resolve this issue. However, an increase in the number of parameters will lead to a decline in the quality of optimization results via the NM algorithm. Consequently, a more computationally expensive optimization algorithm, such as GA, would be required. Conversely, the results based on the NSM-based P-TRF offer highly accurate TRFs comparable to experimental measurements. As is found from the comparison with the ‘Original’ estimates, the improvement over the initial guess is notable, especially for the amplitude components.

The good agreement observed in Figures 6 and 7 also highlights that the present approach, combined with the NSM-based P-TRF, can efficiently estimate the TRFs without the need for time-consuming tests in regular waves across a range of wave frequencies. To further improve accuracy, the introduction of the boundary element method (BEM) (e.g. Mei et al. [20]) could be promising, provided that the BEM is properly parameterized.

Figure 6. Estimated transfer functions by using the CFE- and NSM-based P-TRFs in comparison with experimental measurements using a bulk carrier model (amplitude component), $\beta = 240$ deg.

Figure 7. Estimated transfer functions by using the CFE- and NSM-based P-TRFs in comparison with experimental measurements using a bulk carrier model (phase component), $\beta = 240$ deg.

5.2. Container ship model test ($V = 0$ m/s)

The experimental measurements using the container ship model are referenced to validate the accuracy of the reconstructed waves by Eq. (16), with the introduction of estimated TRFs. For each relative wave direction case, the 1800 s measurements are divided into three 600 s time windows, as $T_e = 300$ s is used. Then, the sum of the respective cost functions (J_1 , J_2 , and J_3) in each time window is then used for optimization. It means, the cost function J is defined as follows such that the cost functions from each time window are summed up:

$$J = J_1 + J_2 + J_3 \quad (25)$$

Given that the CFE-based P-TRF has been demonstrated to be ineffective for estimating the phase components of TRFs, see sub-section 5.1, the focus is now shifted to the use of the NSM-based P-TRF. The initial guess is set as $\{L, B, T, V, \gamma\} = \{283.8, 42.8, 14, 0, 0.75\}$, which refers to the principal particulars, see Figure 4, together with respective β values.

To evaluate the goodness-of-fit of reconstructed wave profiles, the following metric, i.e. the Pearson Correlation Coefficient ρ is introduced:

$$\rho = \frac{\text{cov}(\zeta^e(t), \zeta^{\text{meas}}(t))}{\sigma(\zeta^e(t))\sigma(\zeta^{\text{meas}}(t))} \quad (26)$$

where ζ^{meas} denotes the measured wave elevation. ρ is derived with reference to 1800 s measurements and estimations. For comparison, ρ based on the reconstructed waves by introducing $\{L, B, T, V, \gamma\} = \{283.8, 42.8, 14, 0, 0.75\}$ (and respective β values) are also computed (referred to as ‘Original’).

Table 1 shows the obtained ρ values for the relative wave direction $\beta = 180, 210, 240, 300, 330,$ and 0 deg cases. It is evident that the accuracy of the estimated TRFs is superior to that of the Original results for $\beta = 180,$

and 210 deg cases, thereby substantiating the significance of the present approach. On the other hand, in the other cases, the estimated TRF-based results are somewhat inferior to the Original results. One potential cause of this issue is that the present cost function J given by Eq. (21) is based on the response measurements and estimations, which are in many cases narrow-banded. In turn, the present approach is not capable of accurately estimating the high frequency waves and TRFs in which the heave, pitch, and VBM are less sensitive. In this context, Table 2 compares the metrics focusing on the low frequency components of the measured and estimated waves; ρ values are derived from low-pass filtered time series by applying a frequency threshold of 0.7 rad/s. Evidently, the estimated TRF-based results exhibit high accuracy also in the $\beta = 300, 330$ and 0 deg cases. To enhance the accuracy in the high frequency components, the introduction of other responses that are more susceptible to high frequency waves would be beneficial [9]. Overall improvement compared to the Original results is demonstrated, but it is inferred that the present NSM-based P-TRF may be somewhat insufficient to accurately reproduce the heave, pitch, and VBM TRFs simultaneously in head seas, leading to relatively smaller ρ value in the $\beta = 180$ deg case. Future work could ideally involve enriching the P-TRF, for example, by referencing 3D BEM.

Nonetheless, the estimation performance for the case $\beta = 240$ deg is still not satisfactory. A potential cause for the relatively poor performance is that the NM algorithm converges to unexpected local optima, which does not necessarily represent the global best solution to the problem. To examine this, Bayesian Optimization (BO), implemented by the Matlab function *bayesopt*, is employed to search for the global optima of Eq. (21). After 400 iterations of BO, the resulting ρ values are presented in the tables. The BO results evidently demonstrate a better correlation. In light of this, the BO could be a favorable choice for the present problem, however, care should be taken concerning its computational burdens.

Figure 8 illustrates comparisons of incident wave profiles derived from wave gauge measurements and those based on the estimated TRFs, noting that a low-pass filter with a frequency threshold of 0.7 rad/s has been applied to all the time series. The initial 600 s time series have been subjected to comparison. For the case with $\beta = 240$ deg, the BO-based result is also presented. The reconstructed waves based on the estimated TRFs demonstrate a high degree of correlation with the phase and amplitude of the measured waves, as evidenced by the metrics values presented in Table 2. To complete the optimization using the NSM-based TRFs, the absolute computation time was 1680 s, using the authors' laptop PC (Intel® Core™ i5-1145G7 Processor, 16GB). Given the measurement time length of 1800 s in the present cases, the present approach would be readily implementable in practical operation. In the event that shorter time length measurements are employed, it is necessary to expedite the computational time. One potential solution would be to use a neural network (NN) to train seakeeping codes for TRF computation (in the present study, NSM) and incorporate a well-trained NN into the P-TRF as a surrogate model.

Table 1. ρ based on reconstructed wave profiles using estimated TRFs. Raw measurements and estimations are used.

	Original	Based on estimated TRF
$\beta = 180$ deg (head seas)	-0.066	0.104
$\beta = 210$ deg	0.107	0.344
$\beta = 240$ deg	0.422	0.420
		(Bayesian optimization: 0.612)
$\beta = 300$ deg	0.794	0.731
$\beta = 330$ deg	0.787	0.621
$\beta = 0$ deg (following seas)	0.642	0.704

Table 2. ρ based on reconstructed wave profiles using estimated TRFs. Low-pass filtered measurements and estimations with a threshold frequency of 0.7 rad/s are used.

	Original	Based on estimated TRF
$\beta = 180$ deg (head seas)	-0.004	0.427
$\beta = 210$ deg	0.314	0.473
$\beta = 240$ deg	0.468	0.407
		(Bayesian optimization: 0.782)
$\beta = 300$ deg	0.943	0.947
$\beta = 330$ deg	0.863	0.875
$\beta = 0$ deg (following seas)	0.855	0.870

Figure 8. Comparisons of wave profiles from experimental measurements and reconstructed ones using estimated transfer functions by the NSM-based P-TRFs. A low-pass filter with a threshold frequency of 0.7 rad/s has been applied.

6. Conclusions

This paper demonstrated the effectiveness of a concurrent estimation method of ship response transfer functions (TRFs) and incident waves. The present study employs a methodology that integrates the phase-resolved sea state estimation approach by Takami et al. [15], together with a parametrized TRF (P-TRF). TRFs of ship responses are estimated so that the errors between measured responses and computed responses on the basis of P-TRFs and reconstructed waves are minimized. This approach thus replaces the TRF estimation problem with a parameter identification problem within the P-TRF framework. In the present study, the closed-form expression (CFE) and New Strip Method (NSM) were employed to characterize the P-TRF. The Nelder-Mead (NM) algorithm was employed for the identification of parameters.

Experimental investigations using heave, pitch, and vertical bending moment (VBM) amidships measurements were made. Experimental campaigns using a bulk carrier and container ship models were referenced. Through an experimental investigation, which made use of the bulk carrier test, it was revealed that the CFE-based P-TRFs were unable to provide an accurate estimation of the phase components of the TRFs. In contrast, the NSM-based

P-TRFs demonstrated high accuracy in both the amplitude and phase components of the TRFs. The precision of the wave reconstruction based on the estimated TRFs based on the NSM-based P-TRFs was validated by comparing to containership test measurements. Albeit the inaccuracy in high frequency wave components due to the reduced sensitivity of the responses to high-frequency waves, the reconstructed waves by using the estimated TRFs were found to be accurate overall. In comparison to waves reconstructed using the TRFs with a straightforward reference to the principal particulars, the enhancement through the implementation of the present approach was particularly evident in head seas and oblique head sea cases. It was also demonstrated that the application of a global optimization algorithm, such as Bayesian Optimization, yields favorable results, albeit with a trade-off in computational efficiency.

Computational burdens of the present approach based on the NSM-based P-TRFs are practically acceptable if long time response measurements are used. Expediting the TRF computation would be required if short time response measurements are referred to, which may be attained by utilizing machine learning to train a neural network for TRF computation, and we are currently undertaking this topic (Takami et al. [21]).

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